

FACE DAMAGE GROWTH OF SANDWICH COMPOSITES UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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SUMMARY

Static tests have been performed on sandwich panels with $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ and $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ faces in edge compression with Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID). The failure modes and critical levels of load causing face damage propagation are determined, and compared with an analytical model. Two distinct failure behaviours are observed for each specimen.

Keywords: Edge-compression, static, sandwich structures, C-scan, Digital Image Correlation, impact.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composites are used extensively in many automotive, aerospace and marine industries due to their ability to produce structures with high stiffness-to-weight ratios. There is a continuous need to certify those types of composites under controlled tests. As sandwich panels are prone to impact in many applications, the influence of impact damage on static and fatigue strength has been extensively studied. Sandwich faces resist the compressible forces while the core increases the flexure rigidity. Many researches have studied the damage mechanism of sandwich structures. Rome et al [1] investigated the compressive strength of impacted sandwich panels experimentally. Through their experiments, they indicated that the compression strength after impact was 40% of the undamaged specimens. Kassapoglou et al [2] developed an expression to predict compressive buckling of sandwich panels with elliptical delamination near the sandwich core. They used an eigenvalue buckling analysis [3] to evaluate the buckling and propagation of this artificial delamination. Shipsha et al [4] addressed the effect of low velocity impact damage on post-impact failure mechanisms of foam core sandwich beams with faces of FRP subjected to edgewise compression and bending load cases. Many studies have investigated the post impact behaviour of sandwich structures, e.g. [5] and [6]. The threshold impact energy was defined in previous work by Ambur [7-8] to be the level at which the dominant damage modes are through-thickness shear cracking, delamination, back surface tension failure, core separation and crushing.

Delamination buckling is thought to be one of the major mechanisms for damage propagation in solid laminates loaded in Compression After Impact (CAI). Various mathematical models have been developed to represent delamination growth in composite laminates. Chai et al [9] developed a one-dimensional mathematical model for delamination growth in composite plates. The material properties used in the model were considered to be isotropic, homogenous and linear elastic. As an extension for

their 1-D model, Chai et al [10] developed a 2D delamination-buckling model to study some parameters affecting the growth behaviour such as the initial delamination dimensions, the elastic properties of the cover layer, the Poisson's ratio of the parent medium, the loading history and the fracture energy.

In this study, the CAI strength of a composite-foam sandwich is investigated. A Digital Image Correlation system (DIC) was used to monitor the impact-damaged face behaviour under compressive loading and results were compared to an analytical model [13] for prediction of CAI strength of composite laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Specimens Details

Sandwich specimens were tested under static loading. The core material was 25mm thick Rohacell Polymethacrylamide Foam (110 kg/m^3). The face materials are a mixture of unidirectional glass and carbon fibre prepreg with material properties shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Material properties of Sandwich Faces under Compression

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{1C} (J/m ²)	Thickness (mm)
Fibredux 913 GE5 – Unidirectional Glass	43.9	15.4	4.29	0.28	225	0.142
Hexply 913C HTA (12K)- 47% Unidirectional Carbon	135	18.5	4.97	0.29	225	0.134

Two specimens with $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ faces were tested where subscripts C and G denote carbon and glass respectively. Both had dimensions of 220x100mm. The specimens were impacted by 8J using an Instron/Dynatup impact machine. They were held by a fixture which has a window (75x125mm) and four clamps, and the impactor head was semi-spherical of 16 mm diameter. Both had their 0° fibre direction aligned along the length of the window shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Impact fixture layout

The impact-damaged specimens were scanned by an ultrasonic C-Scan system before testing to visualise the through-thickness damage morphology within the face laminate, see Figure 2. The damage shape had two distinctive morphologies; one was of elliptic shape near the impact surface while the other was of circular shape near the foam side.

Figure 2. C-Scan image of the damage in a $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ face laminate specimen. (Dimensions are in mm and 0° plies are parallel to the x-axis).

In order to further investigate the through-thickness damage morphology before testing, another similar sample impacted by the same energy level was sectioned and visualised under an optical microscope. A section at the centre and along the x-axis showed the longest delamination located after the fourth layer from the impact face with 30 mm length. While another centre section taken across the y-axis showed an average width of 8 mm at the same level and a 20 mm delamination after the twelfth layer near the foam side. It was shown that the elliptic shape appearing in the C-Scan image in Figure 2 was related to the damage near the impact face as visualised by the sectioning technique, despite the difference in dimensions.

Static Test Results

Static tests were performed on two samples to investigate the influence of impact on the static strength. The first was cut into 100x100mm and it was aligned along the loading axis (x-axis) so it had $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ face layup while the second was aligned perpendicular to this with $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ faces. In order to check uniform loading on both sandwich faces, six strain gauges were attached on the impact and back face for each specimen. Figure 3 shows specimen dimensions and strain gauges positions. Gauges 1, 2, 3 and 4 were attached on the impact face while 5 and 6 were on the back face to ensure equal loads were applied on both faces.

In the case of the $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ specimen, the loading behaviour was linear up to failure at load level of 65 kN as shown in Figure 4. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was used to monitor the impacted face deformation and strain under loading. The system consists of two high speed cameras set at equal angles from the specimen axis. A speckle pattern was applied to the specimen face using white paint. The system software from LIMESS[®] uses this speckle pattern to calculate the

displacement, strain and curvature of the loaded face with respect to the initial undeformed state. The damage face buckled away from the foam core as the load increased. Figure 5 shows out-of-plane displacements of the damage face at load levels of 65 kN. Out-of-plane displacements were extracted and plotted along two cut sections in Figures 6 and 7. The results show that out-of-plane displacement occurred above a load level of 15 kN and that it increased as the load increased. They also show that there was significant buckling above 55 kN corresponding to a nominal strain level of approximately 5600 μ strain. At the start of the loading, the buckling distribution was not uniform; it had a cone shape with an elliptic base. The cone major axis was perpendicular to the loading axis and the cone base dimensions increased with increasing the load which shows evidence of damage propagation. The maximum out of plane displacement was 0.7 mm measured at load level of 64 kN corresponding to a nominal strain level of approximately 6800 μ strain.

After the test was performed a section was cut through the first specimen perpendicular to the load direction (i.e along the x-axis) in order to visualise the damage propagation. The specimen had through-width separations at the fourth and twelfth levels from impact side i.e. between the $[(\mp 45_C)_2]$ and $[(90_C, 90_G)_4]$ layer bands.

Figure 3. Sandwich specimen dimensions and strain gauges locations.

Figure 4. Strain measurements for specimen with $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ faces

Figure 5. Out of plane displacements for specimen with $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ faces at 65 kN

Figure 6. Displacement distribution over vertical cut plane (B) in Figure 5 at different compression load levels.

Figure 7. Displacement distribution over vertical cut plane (A) in Figure 5 at different compression load levels.

The specimen with $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ face laminates was potted in special resin containers to prohibit any brooming at the ends while leaving a gauge length of 100mm. Failure occurred at 151 kN corresponding to a nominal strain of approximately 7300 μ strain. In contrast to the previous specimen, buckling was observed to occur towards the foam side. The strain measurements for the test are shown in Figure 8 while Figures 9, 10 and 11 show out of plane displacement distributions for the second specimen. The displacement distribution had a cone shape with a circular base. The maximum out of plane displacement was 1.2 mm with a base diameter of 60 mm and face buckling of the whole specimen was observed after 116 kN. The specimen failure was sudden and cracks appeared on the surface through the whole width.

Figure 8. Strain measurements for specimen with $[(\pm 45C)_2, (0C, 0G)_4, (\pm 45C)_2]$ faces

Figure 9. Out of plane displacement for specimen with $[(\pm 45C)_2, (0C, 0G)_4, (\pm 45C)_2]$ faces at 151 kN

Figure 10. Displacement distribution over vertical cut plane (B) in Figure 9 at different compression load levels.

Figure 11. Displacement distribution over vertical cut plane (A) in Figure 9 at different compression load levels.

ANALYTICAL MODELING

In order to evaluate the threshold strain to be applied to the specimen, a theoretical analysis was performed using VICONOPT [11]. The software calculates the critical strain level for a delaminated sub-laminate to buckle from which it is possible to determine the strain at which propagation of the damage occurs from previous work by Butler et al [12] and Read et al [13]. The software models the plate as a series of finite strips; their edges are constrained by nodes approximating a circular or elliptic boundary, as in Figure 12, along which the plate is assumed to be clamped. This critical strain depends on the face layup, delamination size and its position within the layers of the laminate. Unit axial compression strain was applied to the full laminate (both laminated faces of the sandwich) before the load vector acting on the delaminated plate sublaminates was obtained assuming compatibility around the delamination perimeter. This load vector was entered into VICONOPT to obtain the critical buckling strain of the sublaminates produced by the delamination. Using the following equation derived by Rhead et al [13], the threshold strain at which the damage propagates is calculated:

$$\varepsilon_{th} = \varepsilon^c \left(\sqrt{4 + \frac{2G_{1C}}{(\varepsilon^c)^2 A_{11}}} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

where ε_{th} , ε^c , A_{11} , G_{1C} are the threshold strain, buckling strain, axial stiffness of the sublaminates in the direction of load and strain energy release rate for critical mode I, respectively.

Figure 12. Thin-film model showing VICONOPT strip model of post-buckled circular and elliptical delaminated plate

The model was used to predict the buckling and threshold strain for the face laminate of both specimens described in the previous section. The scanned image showed different damage morphologies through the face thickness while the sectioning technique showed the maximum damage existed after the fourth layer. DIC results taken for the $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ specimen showed that the buckled damage area had an elliptic base area of 18x30 mm at a load level of 55 kN. This area was chosen as it resembled clamped-clamped boundary condition (i.e. zero slopes of the displacement curves). The dimensions were used to model an elliptic plate of four layers for both specimens but with different orientations of the axes. Table 2 represents the buckling strains for the delaminated area for both face laminates. The threshold strain for propagation at ply level four, calculated for the $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ laminate using Equation (1), was 6130 μ strain.

Table 2: Buckling strains for both face laminates with an elliptic damage, assuming that the delamination damage exists after the fourth ply.

Laminate	Plate dimensions a x b (mm)	ε^c (10^{-6})
$[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$	30x18	5310
$[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$	18x30	13300

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In order to determine the damage morphology through the face thickness, C-Scan and sectioning techniques were used. The C-Scan image for the damage showed that it was of elliptical shape with dimensions 38x10 mm. By sectioning another impact-damaged sample without testing, the longest damage existed between the fourth and fifth layers from the impact side. The damage was observed to be 30x6 mm. The difference of damage dimensions from the C-Scan image and the section was thought to be because the C-Scan image captured the damage within the whole layers of the face which was spread through different layers while the dimensions from the section showed the longest one. From the static test results for the sample with $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ laminate, the buckling behaviour of the damage area on the impact surface was of elliptic shape similar to the C-Scan image shown in Figure 1. From the out of plane displacement graphs in Figures 6 and 7, the shape of the displacement cone had an elliptic base of 30x18 mm. Propagation, which was predicted to occur at 6130 μ strain, was observed in the experiment at a nominal strain of approximately 6000 μ strain. Failure did not occur until the nominal strain of 6800 μ strain. This additional capacity is thought to be due to the remaining bending stiffness of the sandwich system following propagation.

In order to understand the different buckling behaviour of each specimen, a pre-developed model by Rhead et al [13] was used to calculate the buckling strains of an elliptical damage area of the aforementioned dimensions as it represents an approximation of the delamination area within the laminate between the fourth and fifth layers (as observed from sectioning). The model showed that the theoretical buckling would occur at strain levels of 5310 and 13300 μ strain for $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ and $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminates respectively. However, the latter specimen exhibited face buckling of the damage face towards the foam with 60 mm base diameter. To understand why this mode occurred for this specimen rather than the first one, VICONOPT was used to study face buckling of the full laminates as a circular plate 60 mm diameter. The area was chosen to roughly approximate the support provided by the foam core around the depression created by the initial impact assuming equivalent clamped-clamped boundary conditions. The model showed that face buckling would occur at 23000 and 11000 μ strain for $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ and $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminates, respectively. Whilst these values do not reflect the experimental values of buckling strain, they do show that for the first specimen, the sub-laminate buckling strain was less than the buckling strain for the whole laminate, so sub-laminate buckling took place prior to buckling-driven propagation of the face damage. While for the $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminate, face buckling occurred because the buckling strain for the face laminate was less than the sub-laminate buckling strain. Figure 13 shows different buckling modes for both laminates.

Similar results were concluded by Hunt et al [14] who developed a nonlinear model for delaminated struts under compression loading. They showed that an opening or closing mode would depend on the position and length of the delamination; long, near surface delaminations are more likely to produce an opening mode. Their model assumed that the laminates were made of isotropic materials. The present study showed that a

delamination depth to total thickness ratio of 0.25 in the $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ laminate resulted in an opening mode. While the same ratio in the $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminate produced a closing mode because of material anisotropy and face-foam interaction which affects the boundary conditions of the damaged area. Although the level of nominal strain at which failure occurred was similar, the failure stress of the $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminate was 130% higher than that of the $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ laminate.

(a) Sub-laminate buckling mode for $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ laminate

(b) Face buckling mode for $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ laminate

Figure 13 Different buckling modes of the two specimens

CONCLUSIONS

Sandwich specimens with $[(\mp 45_C)_2, (90_C, 90_G)_4, (\mp 45_C)_2]$ and $[(\pm 45_C)_2, (0_C, 0_G)_4, (\pm 45_C)_2]$ face laminates were tested under compression after impact. Failure was shown to be dependent on the orientation of fibres at the centre of the laminates. When these fibres are at 90° to the loading direction, an opening of the delamination was observed giving rise to buckling-driven propagation which has been successfully predicted using a semi-analytical technique. However, when these fibres are parallel to the direction of load, the opening of delamination was not observed and the fibres buckled into a core depression arising from the impact. It has been shown that the propensity of this latter mode can be predicted because of the high initial buckling strain of the sublaminates produced by the delamination compared with full face laminate buckling.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Rome, J.I., Schubel, P.M., Goyal, V.K., Tuck-Lee, J., "Predicting compression-after impact strength of composite sandwich structures", 49th

AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials 7-10, Schaumburg, IL, April 2008.

- [2] Kassapoglou, C., Abbott R.,” A correlation parameter for predicting the compressive strength of composite sandwich panels after low speed impact”, AIAA-1988-2294, Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, 29th, Williamsburg, VA, Apr 18-20, p. 642-650, 1988.
- [3] Kassapoglou, C.,” Buckling, post-buckling and failure of elliptical delaminations in laminates under compression”, Journal of Composite Structures Vol.9, p.p 139-159, 1988
- [4] Shipsha, A., Hallström, S., Zenkert, D.,”Failure Modelling of Impact Damage in Sandwich Beams- A 2D Approach: Part I – Experimental Investigation”, Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials; Vol 5, 2003.
- [5] Kardomateas, G.A., "Postbuckling characteristics in delaminated kevlar/epoxy laminates: an experimental study", Journal of Composites Technology and Research (ASTM), vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 85-90., 1990.
- [6] Edgren, F., Asp, L.E., "Compressive Failure of Impacted NCF Composite Sandwich Panels –Characterisation of the Failure Process", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 38, 495, 2004.
- [7] Ambur, D.R. , Cruz J.,” Low-speed impact response characteristics of composite sandwich panels”, AIAA 95-1460-CP, 36th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC SDM-Conference, 4:2681-2689, 1995.
- [8] Ambur, D.R., Starnes, J. H. Jr., "Effect of curvature on the impact damage characteristics and residual strength of composite plates", 39th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, Long Beach, California, Aug 1992.
- [9] Chai, H., Babcock, C.D., Knauss, W.,” One Dimensional Modelling of Failure in Laminated Plates by Delamination Buckling”, International Journal of Solids and Structures. Vol.17, No.11, pp. 1069-1083, 1981.
- [10] Chai, H., Babcock, C.D. “Two-dimensional modelling of compressive failure in delaminated laminates”. Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.19, Jan, p.67-98, 1985.
- [11] Williams, F.W., Anderson, M.S., Kennedy, D., Butler, R., Aston, G.,” User manual for VICONOPT”, NASA CR-181966, 1990
- [12] Butler, R., Almond, D.P., Hunt, G.W., Hu, B., Gathercole, N.,” Compressive fatigue limit of impact damaged composite laminates”, Journal of Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 38, pp 1211-1215, 2001.
- [13] Rhead, A.T., Butler, R., Hunt, G.W., “Post-buckled propagation model for compressive fatigue of impact damaged laminates” International J of Solids & Structures. 45 (16), pp. 4349-4361, 2008.
- [14] Hunt, G.W., Hu, B., Butler, R., Almond, D.P., Wright, J.E., “Nonlinear modeling of delaminated struts”, AIAA Journal, Vol.42, No. 11, November 2004.